

UZBEKISTAN'S PARTICIPATION IN THE TIMSS 2023 INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT: RESULTS, CONCLUSIONS, AND STRATEGIC OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract. *This article examines Uzbekistan's participation in the TIMSS 2023 international assessment program, focusing on the methodology, results, and conclusions of the study. TIMSS evaluates students' mathematics and science knowledge worldwide. The findings of this research are significant for aligning Uzbekistan's education system with international standards and for making strategic decisions to improve students' knowledge levels.*

Keywords: *TIMSS 2023, international assessment, mathematics, science, education quality improvement, Uzbekistan, international education system, methodology, students, education strategy.*

Introduction

TIMSS (Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study) is a prestigious international assessment program designed to evaluate the mathematics and science knowledge of Grade 4 and Grade 8 students across many countries.[1] This program serves as a vital resource for analyzing the quality of education, assessing the effectiveness of curricula, and shaping educational models that meet international standards. TIMSS not only measures student achievement levels but also explores pedagogical approaches, classroom processes, and the general state of educational resources. [2] Moreover, the program identifies differences and similarities among national education systems, providing a foundation for learning from successful practices and implementing them effectively.

Uzbekistan's participation in the TIMSS 2023 program is a step toward strengthening the country's position in the international education arena, developing the national education system, and enhancing its efficiency.[3] This initiative is being implemented as part of the “Year of attention to human and quality education” within the framework of the “New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022–2026”, approved by Presidential Decree PD-27 dated February 28, 2023.[4] Clause 175 of this strategy emphasizes advancing the quality of education to a new level by ensuring Uzbekistan's participation in international assessment programs. This participation holds significant importance for achieving strategic goals aimed at assessing and enhancing the competitiveness of Uzbekistan's education system on a global scale.

The implementation of the TIMSS program in Uzbekistan required significant changes aimed at developing students' knowledge and skills in alignment with international assessment systems. [2, 5] This involved aligning national curricula with international standards and focusing on enhancing students' scientific and logical thinking abilities. Modern pedagogical approaches, innovative technologies, and training programs tailored to the international assessment system were developed for educators. Additionally, school infrastructure was improved to provide students with comfortable and effective learning opportunities.[3, 6]

In April-May 2023, Uzbekistan conducted the trial processes of the TIMSS 2023 international student assessment program. Through this study, the current state of the national education system was analyzed based on international criteria, and proposals aimed at improving the quality of education were developed. Students from Grades 4 and 8, selected from schools across various regions of Uzbekistan, participated in this process. This provided an opportunity not only to evaluate the students' level of knowledge but also to assess the effectiveness of teaching methods, curricula, and infrastructure [1, 4].

The data collected within the framework of TIMSS 2023 serves not only to determine the level of students' knowledge but also provides a foundation for making strategic decisions to improve the national education system. The results of this study act as important indicators for aligning the country's education system with international standards, modernizing curricula, and implementing modern pedagogical technologies [5, 7].

Literature Review

Directors of the TIMSS and PIRLS International Study Center, Mullis, I.V.S., & Hooper, M.: TIMSS continues to assess students' knowledge of mathematics and science worldwide. In this process, Uzbekistan's strengths and weaknesses are analyzed to highlight its position at the international level. As a result, the outcomes of Uzbekistan can be compared with international rankings, allowing for the identification of strengths and weaknesses.

TIMSS Official Website: <https://timssandpirls.bc.edu>: This online platform provides opportunities to analyze TIMSS program results within a global context. Data from the website has been utilized to present statistical evidence for the article.

Presidential Decree PD-27 of February 28, 2023: The decree outlines tasks related to participation in international studies. Specifically, it establishes strategies for ensuring Uzbekistan's involvement in international assessment programs, including the TIMSS program, and enables the selection of participants and the evaluation of their knowledge through random sampling.

UNESCO Information: Data published by UNESCO offers insights into global developments in education and the analysis of TIMSS results. This, in turn, provides an international context for Uzbekistan's education system.

Methodology

The TIMSS 2023 study in Uzbekistan was implemented by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) in collaboration with the Ministry of Preschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. As part of this process, 8,800 students (4,450 from Grade 4 and 4,350 from Grade 8) from 166 schools selected across all regions of Uzbekistan participated in tests and questionnaires focusing on mathematics literacy and science [2, 6]. This process was conducted in strict adherence to international assessment standards.

Additionally, 166 school principals and 1,035 mathematics and science teachers from these schools participated in the surveys. The data collected during the study enabled the measurement of students' knowledge levels, the analysis of the effectiveness of pedagogical approaches, and the evaluation of the impact of school management on the quality of education. [4, 5]

The students participating in the study completed test assignments developed by the TIMSS program based on international standards. The test materials aimed to assess students' logical thinking, problem-solving, and ability to apply theoretical knowledge in practice in mathematics and science.[1] The surveys designed for teachers and school principals focused on

the organization of the educational process, efforts to improve the quality of curricula, and identifying challenges faced during the learning process.

The collected data was analyzed in collaboration with international organizations, and recommendations were developed to enhance the country's education system. The results of this study played an important role in improving the quality of education in Uzbekistan by integrating it with international assessment systems.

Results and Discussion

The TIMSS 2023 results clearly demonstrated a strong correlation between the school environment and the quality of education. The study confirmed that factors such as the material and technical resources of schools, conditions provided for students, teacher qualifications, and innovative approaches in the educational process significantly impact quality indicators. Specifically, creating a comfortable and safe learning environment, utilizing modern teaching tools, and increasing parental involvement were identified as contributing factors to improving educational quality. The TIMSS findings emphasize the need for further in-depth exploration of these factors.

Results of Uzbekistan's 8th-grade students in TIMSS 2023

According to preliminary analysis based on the draft version of the international report, the average mathematics literacy score of Uzbekistan's 8th-grade students was 421 points, placing them 32nd out of 44 participating countries. In science literacy, the 8th-grade students scored an average of 396 points, ranking 39th among the 44 participating countries.

Results of 4th-grade students: In science literacy, Uzbekistan's 4th-grade students scored an average of 412 points, ranking 54th out of 58 participating countries. In mathematics literacy, they achieved an average score of 443 points, placing 50th among the 58 countries. Uzbekistan outperformed several countries in the study: in mathematics literacy, it surpassed Saudi Arabia (420), South Africa (362), and Brazil (400). In science literacy, Uzbekistan scored higher than Kosovo (403), Morocco (390), and South Africa (308).

For reference, the top-performing countries for 4th-grade students were Singapore (615 points in mathematics and 607 points in science), Chinese Taipei (607 points in mathematics and 573 points in science), and Korea (594 points in mathematics and 583 points in science). For 8th-grade students, the highest-scoring countries were Singapore (605 points in mathematics and 606 points in science), Chinese Taipei (602 points in mathematics and 572 points in science), and Korea (596 points in mathematics and 545 points in science).

In Uzbekistan, 4th-grade girls scored 441 points in mathematics, while boys scored 446 points. In science, girls achieved 410 points, and boys scored 414 points. For 8th-grade students, girls and boys scored nearly the same in science, with girls achieving 395 points and boys scoring 396 points. However, in mathematics, boys outperformed girls, scoring 426 points compared to 416 points for girls.

Information about teachers of students participating in TIMSS 2023

In the TIMSS 2023 study, school teachers were asked about their qualifications. According to data provided by school teachers in Uzbekistan, 71% of 8th-grade mathematics teachers hold a bachelor's degree (ISCED Level 6), while 7% hold a master's degree (ISCED Level 7). The percentage of teachers with a master's degree is 33% on the international average. Analysis revealed that the proportion of teachers in Uzbekistan with a bachelor's degree is higher than the international average of 53%.

A deeper analysis of the results of Uzbek students participating in the study based on their responses to the questionnaires can be summarized in the following report:

Figure 1. Comparison of boys' and girls' average scores in mathematics and science for 4th and 8th grades in TIMSS 2023.

Results of 4th-grade students:

Students whose parents have completed higher education (1) scored an average of 477 points in mathematics, while students whose parents have only completed school/college/lyceum (2) scored an average of 432 points. In science, this gap remained consistent, with (1) scoring an average of 445 points and (2) achieving an average of 401 points.

Fourth-grade students who attended a preschool institution for 1 year or less scored an average of 437 points in mathematics, while those who attended for 3 years or more achieved 452 points. In science, fourth-grade students who attended a preschool institution for 1 year or less scored an average of 407 points, whereas those who attended for 3 years or more scored 418 points.

In mathematics, fourth-grade students from high socio-economic status backgrounds scored an average of 497 points, while students from low socio-economic status backgrounds scored an average of 426 points. In science, fourth-grade students from high socio-economic status backgrounds scored an average of 462 points, compared to an average of 395 points for students from low socio-economic status backgrounds.

Fourth-grade students with 0-10 books at home scored an average of 427 points in mathematics, while those with 26-100 books scored an average of 466 points. In science, fourth-grade students with 0-10 books at home scored an average of 396 points, whereas those with 26-100 books scored an average of 434 points.

Fourth-grade students with a computer (laptop) at home scored an average of 458 points in mathematics, while those without a computer (laptop) scored an average of 434 points. In science, fourth-grade students with a computer (laptop) at home scored an average of 424 points, whereas those without a computer (laptop) scored an average of 404 points.

Results of 8th-grade students

Eighth-grade students who considered mathematics lessons boring scored an average of 403 points, while those who disagreed with this view scored an average of 439 points.

Students whose parents had completed higher education (1) scored an average of 418 points in mathematics, while students whose parents had only completed school/college/lyceum (2)

scored an average of 385 points. In science, this gap remained consistent, with (1) scoring an average of 445 points and (2) achieving an average of 413 points.

Eighth-grade students with 0-10 books at home scored an average of 396 points in mathematics, while those with 26-100 books scored an average of 440 points. In science, students with 0-10 books at home scored an average of 374 points, whereas those with 26-100 books scored an average of 413 points.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The TIMSS 2023 results played a significant role in determining Uzbekistan's position in the international education arena. This study provided a foundation for analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of the education system in Uzbekistan, identifying existing shortcomings, and making strategic decisions to improve the quality of education.

In conclusion, further improvement of the national education system is required to enable students to achieve results aligned with international standards in mathematics and science. The following areas are recommended for focused efforts:

Updating pedagogical approaches: It is necessary to introduce innovative teaching methods aimed at developing creativity and analytical thinking skills.

Expanding practical activities: To enhance students' practical and experimental knowledge, it is essential to extensively utilize laboratory exercises and interactive educational tools.

Improving teacher qualifications: Teachers need to be trained to meet international standards by introducing modern methodologies and technologies, and their professional development should be supported.

Modernizing curricula: Curricula should be updated based on international requirements and trends, with a focus on developing analytical and logical thinking skills.

Enhancing school infrastructure: The learning process should be supported by providing modern laboratories, information technologies, and educational resources.

Monitoring results: The education system should be continuously monitored based on international assessment results, and updates should be implemented in alignment with the findings.

The TIMSS 2023 results marked an important step for Uzbekistan in further developing its education system and achieving a competitive level on the international stage. These results provide an opportunity to reassess existing resources, develop new strategies, and enhance achievements through the extensive integration of technologies into the education system. With its potential and adaptability to global trends, Uzbekistan's education system has the capacity to make successful strides on the international arena.

REFERENCES

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2023-yil 28-fevraldagi PF-27-sonli Farmoni.
2. Mullis, I.V.S., & Martin, M.O. (Eds.). (2023). TIMSS 2023 International Results in Mathematics and Science.
3. TIMSS xalqaro natijalari sharhi: Mullis, I.V.S., & Hooper, M. (2023).
4. TIMSS rasmiy veb-sayti: <https://timssandpirls.bc.edu>.
5. UNESCO Institut for Statistics ma'lumotlari (2023).
6. <https://www.avloniy.uz/uz/news/lissabonda-timss-2023-xalqaro-tadqiqotining-natijalari>.
7. Xalq ta'limi info <https://xalqta'liminfo.uz/post/979>